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A COMPETENCY MODEL FOR DETERMINING AND ADVANCING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF ENGINEERING FACULTY AT PRIVATE ENGINEERING COLLEGES IN DELHI NCR

Ms Shadma Parveen

Associate professor Alfalah university, Faridabad, Haryana, India

Daleep Parimoo

Professor, Sharda University , Gr. Noida, U.P. India

Abstract:

The current research is based on pilot study conducted focused on determining the demographic and professional profiles and competencies of professors teaching at the private engineering institutions. The researcher has developed and validated an advance practice competency model for engineering faculty. This research focuses on group interviews with the experienced Engineering faculty: Framework mapped against the practice of leading edge practitioner drawn from basically the experienced mechanical engineering faculty of few private engineering colleges of Delhi NCR.

The findings of the study will be used for decision makers in order to create a program for faculty evaluation and improvement at the Engineering Institutions. From the literature review of various world renowned accreditation agencies 74 sub competencies were identified and grouped into eight competency domains. Consensus focus group discussion validates the descriptor terms used to define the competency at 'foundation'. Mastery over the subject, or excellence level practices practitioner mapped their practice using the framework. The majority indicated that their practice was at the mastery for the expert practice.

This study has developed an evidence-based advanced practice competency framework grounded in the multi disciplinary literature and validate by the expert opinion. This provides a map of key generic skills, knowledge and attributes required by individual practicing as a teacher in the Engineering Institutions. The competencies and descriptors developed by this research could be used as a template for the engineering faculty. As this is a pilot study, the proposed model will further be evaluated with large sample size covering the broader geographic areas.

Key Words: Competency, Competency Model, Faculty Development Programmes, NITTTR, Professional Advancement, Engineering Institutions.

Introduction:

Success at a job requires a level of competence. Very few would disagree with that. But defining what makes people competent is not easy to answer. Certainly, if a job needs only a few simple tasks, competency can be easy to determine. But what about the complexities that engineers has to face in the management of technology? How many competencies does an engineer need? And how can they be identified? And developed by the teachers. This kind of fundamental understanding is gaining importance in today's rapid advancement, not only for constant improvement but also to assure continuity. As the professional workforce ages, companies of any kind need to understand the competencies of their engineers. A clear

grasp and understanding of the knowledge needed by engineers will help companies look forward that critical capabilities do not retire from the workplace along with older professionals.

As the old saying goes that the destiny of the nation is determined in its class room but this is the time to realize that the destiny of nation is largely depend on its teachers, how efficiently and effectively they instruct and develop their students as a future engineer . As competent engineers are regarded as the nation builder. But this kind of engineers cannot be produced in the absence of
Competent faculty.

In India, like in many other developing countries, the development of future engineering faculty is utmost important, still remains untouched no serious consideration is paid in maximum number of private institutions except some reputed institutions, are very few in numbers. In recent decades, there has been an increasing concern about the quality of preparation provided at The National Institute of Technical Teachers Training and Research, (an autonomous institution established under the Ministry of Human Resource Development) Government of India with a view to enhance the standard of Technical Education in the Country in general and the Southern Region in particular. In this era of choices, Technical Education specially engineering streams still occupy as a favoured discipline by more than 60% science students. There are more than 4000 engineering colleges in India approved by the All India Council of Technical Education (AICTE). In every college, the Faculty forms the most valuable resource for their growth and achievement. With the rapid advancement in engineering and technology and its adoption by Indian industry occurring at a rapid pace, it has become necessary that the technical teachers should develop an aptitude for lifelong learning and have an exposure to recent advancement in their field through Faculty Development Programmes (FDP). FDP has been recognized as a priority area for Engineering and Polytechnics faculty. In recognition to this, maximum Private Institutions took initiation and started conducting a variety of short term and long term training programmes and short-term courses for their teachers to enable them to acquire competencies relevant to their respective areas of work. The courses cover content updating particularly in new technologies, use of innovative instructional methods and approaches, design and development of learning resources and general management and development of institutional programmes. The AICTE has recognized the short term training programmes conducted by NITTTR for consideration the purpose of movement to higher grades under the Career Advancement Scheme. The NITTTR Faculty who have developed rich expertise in their areas of specialization, undertake consultancy and research work, contribute in the design and conduct of these programmes. The concern for improving the quality of teaching at engineering institutions is one of the main priority established in the Institutional Program for Improving the standard of engineering. NITTTR is part of larger program entitled Program for the Transformation and Improvement of Engineering Institution this includes the following strategies for improving the quality of teacher training and education:

- a) Curriculum reform
- b) Faculty actualization and professional development.
- c) Elaboration and explanation of norms for faculty and orientations for guiding institutional management and regulation of academic work
- d) Improvement of institutional facilities and equipment at the engineering institutions.

Based on the strategic needs established by these policy documents of NITTTR, this research emphasises on the area of faculty actualization and professional advancement. The findings of this study will be used for decision makers in order to create a program for faculty evaluation and improvement at the Engineering Institutions in India. The study centred on professors who are responsible to prepare future Engineers.

The research also responds to the limited number of studies about the academic processes that take place inside the system for preparing teachers at the Engineering institute in Delhi NCR. Given the small number of studies in this area, it is necessary to determine what the professional profiles are of those preparing future teachers at the engineering institutions, particularly under a Competency Model. The word "competence" taken from Latin which means "competere" which means attitude aptitude, expertise, experiences, and other characteristics of competence in performing an activity or in participating in a specific matter (Giraldo & Acuña 2005). Furthermore, competence has obtain a new meaning in Psychological and educational settings and relates to three aspects: 1) achievement, 2) Excellency, and 3) knowledge of a particular domain . According to ISO 9000:2000, competence can be defined as a demonstrated ability to apply knowledge and skills (Blank 1982) and, as and Lloyd and Cook (1993) pointed out, competence is the ability to perform activities to the expected within employment. Janwongpaisan (2006) also explained it as "Skills, knowledge and attribute of a person essential to their work and to their work achievement." White and Mc Clelland (Janwongpaisan 2006) were the first scholars to propose the idea of competence in journals related to human resource development, explaining the relationship of excellent performer and the level of knowledge, skills, and abilities.

Theoretical framework

General competencies are developed in the classroom by participating in community activities etc. In this way, competencies are a result of integrating the learning experiences, (including capacities, skills, and knowledge in a compacted way), in relation to the task for which they are developed. The construction of competency models is required for the standardization and indexation of different types of performance, the formulation and use of competencies require the development of three interactive, but different components: (a) description of the competency; (b) means necessary for measuring and assessing the competency; and (c) the standard by which someone will be judged as a competent professional (Jones y Voorhees, 2002).

Competency models allow the identification of skill, knowledge attitudes and behaviour that are more important for successful achievement of a specific task. So, researcher describes the competencies using behavioural indicators, can be identified when they are present (Mansfield, 2000). Researcher could defined as the element of a competency model: (a) the name of the competency; (b) the statements that define in a behavioural way the competency in action, and (c) the knowledge that is behind the competency, and makes it applicable to a specific task.

As Spencer (2000) has mentioned, competency models are generally presented in a graphic form to show the existing relationships between different domains of the competency, and between different kinds of competencies. As these examples represents, a graphic could show that knowledge competencies are less important than behavioural competencies, or that competencies related to personnel effectiveness are more important than behavioural competencies.

According to Spencer (2000) Competency models reflect the context of the educational institution and communicate the values of the organization, if they are constructed with the participation and effort of experts, those who have demonstrated to be the best in performing the competencies required for the successful performance at work or specific task.

So The competency model, well designed and defined, includes complex competencies to guide the successful accomplishment of a certain task in a particular context, the definitions of each competency, and a list of each observable behaviour for each competency, describes how the competency that is defined can be manifested in each moment of the execution of the specific task .

The use of a competency model in faculty preparation can be very useful for (a) identifying the key competencies for accomplishing institutional goals and objectives; (b) describing competencies at the level of observable behaviours, and make sure that they go beyond a list of characteristics (e.g. self-reliance, adaptability, integrity and maturity, etc.); incorporates with the competencies and behaviours related to the system of educational development of the institution (for example the recruitment, the selection, development, estimation and compensation). In this way, the recognition of teacher profiles for the training centres, responsible to prepare the future Engineering teachers, contrasting with the objectives, purposes and the results of the Engineering institutions, are useful elements for developing concrete processes of academic professional advancement that can lead the engineering teachers at those institutions to develop needed competencies for the achievement of institutional goals.

Objectives

In this paper researcher aimed to design the demographic and professional profiles and competencies of professors teaching at the Engineering institutes of Delhi NCR. The main objectives of this research are the following:

- ❖ To describe the demographic profiles of faculty members of private Engineering Institutes
- ❖ To *develop an advance practice competency model for faculty members.*
- ❖ To analyse the relationship between the professional competencies of the faculty members and the educational outcomes in their institutions.

Methodology

This research utilizes the use of quantitative and qualitative methods of data collection. In order to decide what ideal competencies should be required by the professors at Engineering institutions, the researcher undertook the focus group interviews with faculty members at the six engineering institutions in the region. As a result of these focus group interviews, the researcher identified a list of ideal soft as well as the hard competencies (knowledge, skills, and attitudes).

Then, the researcher developed a questionnaire to identify what the real competencies of current faculty at the Engineering institutions are needed.

Data was collected from 75 faculty members from six Engineering Institute in the region. Table 1 provides some descriptive information about the faculty:

Engineering Institutes	GENDER		TOTAL
	MALES	FEMALES	
Al-Falah University	6	7	13
Brown Hills College Of Engg. And Tech	5	6	11
Manavrachna University	7	5	12
Sharda University	7	5	12
Amity University	9	5	14
Rawal Institute Of Engineering And Technology	7	6	13
TOTAL	41	34	78

Table 1. Faculty members who participated in the focus groups at Engineering Institutes

Additional information was collected from the 25 faculty members (10 males and 15 females) having experience of more than 15 years of instructing engineers at reputed Engineering Institutes selected for the pilot study.

Results

The findings of the first step of this study demonstrates that there is a list of ideal competencies that faculty members, teaching at the Engineering Institution should acquired:

SKILLS	KNOWLEDGE	ATTITUDE	BEHAVIOUR
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Coaching and Training skills. -Presentation Skill. -Technical Skill. -Problem solving skill. -Communication skill. -Technical skill. -Curriculum planning. -Curriculum setting. -Research methodology. -Innovating strategies. -Students' learning process. -Adolescent learning needs and characteristics. -Modular Employable skill. -General culture. -Teaching methods, process, models and approaches. -Pedagogic skills. -Characteristics of institution context. -Study materials and notes for Student. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Knowledge of the specialised subject. -Applied subjects. -General awareness. -Latest innovation and inventions. -Latest trends and researches. -Creating a learning environment. -Formulating learning strategies. -Applying theory to practice. -Utilization of educational media and instructional materials. -Undertaking educational research. -Presenting high teaching skills. -Reviewing assignments and providing feedback. -Organizing artistic activities . -Involving in creative work. -Developing the creativity for students. -Evaluating student counselling and Advising students. -Working with Team spirit -Motivating students. -Enhancing competencies of students. -Demonstrating the relationship among different course contents. -Creating a relationship between teaching and learning. -Identifying and solving discipline problems in the classroom. -Having Command on communication both on oral and written. -Coordinating, supervising students. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Divergent thinking. -Confidence. -Optimistic outlook. -Assertive approach. -Practical. -Adaptability. -Researcher. -Technical. -Qualitative. -Quantitative. -Being sensible towards student needs. -Life long learning. -Being self-controlled. -Being an affective person. -Human development. -Modelling values -Preparing creative people. -Interested in reading on different issue. - Working with peers, seniors and students. -Motivated for careers and professional development -Working well with others. -Open to learn from everyone. -Moving towards a holistic approach. -Promoting an ecological consciousness among students. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Assertiveness -Competitiveness -High moral value -Conduct -Self Sufficiency -Quick decision maker. -Enthusiastic, zeal and zest, -Energetic -Alertness -Boldness -stress tolerance. -stay calm -situational. -Interpersonal relationship.

As the finding exhibits and demonstrates the evident that for the different engineering faculty members who participated in the focus groups was more important for the development of teacher skills or abilities than their knowledge and attitudes. Furthermore, the participants identified the main roles and responsibilities that are expected from an

engineering professor responsible for preparing future Engineers. The main roles identified from this study were the following:

- Teacher (facilitator, evaluator, communicator, developer, innovator, planner and counsellor)
- Tutor (mentor, guide)
- Administrator (manager, supervisor, department head, leader, organiser, coordinator,)
- Advisor (consultant, counsellor)
- Researcher (editor, problem solver, innovator.)

At this juncture of the research process, the researcher have collected all data from the pilot study and administered the modified version of the questionnaire to all engineering students at the Engineering Institutions of Delhi NCR, participating in the study. It is expected that by the end of 2014, the researcher will conclude the process of data collection, analysis and interpretation.

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Appendix:

NAME: (OPTIONAL).....	SPECIALIZATION:
DESIGNATION: ATTENDED: YES/NO	PEDAGOGY TRAINING
INSTITUTION: PROGRAMM ATTENDED	NUMBER OF TRAINING
QUALIFICATION TERMINAL:	DATE OF LAST TRAINING:
TEACHING EXPERIENCE:	DURATION OF LAST TRAINING:
AGE: INSOURSING/OUTSOURSING	TRAINING ATTENDED:
GENDER: INSTITUTIONS:	NAME OF TRAINING
DATE:	

This instrument will help to analyze teaching competencies. Below are the roles and responsibilities that teachers are expected to perform. Against each role/function five categories of responses and their numerical equivalentents are given.

Read each statement carefully given below and indicate how often you behave a particular way. There is no right or wrong answer. You will learn about yourself if you respond to each item as candidly as possible. Answer each statement seriously (please do not leave any statement unanswered).

Tick 1 if you rarely or never behave this way.

Tick 2 if you occasionally behave this way.

Tick 3 if you sometimes behave this way.

Tick 4 if you often behave this way.

Tick 5 if you almost always behave this way.

1) Being Student Centric:

SN.	Teaching Competencies	1	2	3	4	5
1	I identify my student's needs and expectations.					
2	I design and develop the new processes/ procedures/ models to make teaching & learning easy and interesting.(strike out whichever is not applicable)					
3	I create an encouraging/supportive environment during my lectures.					
4	I provide learning material at the appropriate time to my students.					
5	I solve student's problems in friendly / professional manner. (strike out whichever is not applicable)					
6	I strategically plan career paths for individual student.					
7	I am enthused by new ideas and tend to overwhelm my students.					
8	I change my approach if it helps students to develop better.					
9	I arrange the materials which are not easily available to students.					
10	If I am not able to answer the questions, I try to divert my students.					
11	I support my students, even after the course is already completed.					
12	I prepare my students according to market needs and demands.					
13	I maximize the availability for tutorial and pastoral work.					
14	I take students' feedback to enhance my teaching effectiveness.					

2) Teaching and Course Development:

15	I disseminate new methods in teaching and learning.					
16	I design and develop the existing / new courses, content / curriculum (Strike out whichever is not applicable).					
17	I develop benchmark for teaching in terms of content delivery.					
18	I integrate and contribute to inter-disciplinary subjects.					
19	I plan in advance for tutorials/ guidance, maintain teacher's diary /course file.					
20	I cover only those topics in my teaching which are already prescribed.					
21	I create effectiveness in assessment and evaluation procedure.					

3) Responsibility taking:

22	I contribute towards the college mission, vision/goals.					
23	I take responsibility of my actions.					
24	I am self reliant, self dependent and work without supervision					
25	I motivate students for field work and practical experience.					
26	I maintain physical as well as material resources.					
27	I tolerate stress and stay calm in demanding situations.					
28	I monitor and educate others around against unsafe acts and conditions.					
29	I review/mentor other staff.					
30	I represent the Department/Institution in the wider environment.					
31	I build confidence and capability through training and coaching.					
32	I align individual objectives and goals in the team and department					

4) Building Interpersonal and Communication Relationships:

33	I communicate clearly, concisely, confidently in an understandable / accessible language.					
34	I recognize and respect diversity.					
35	I use a variety of written and oral communication.					
36	I use appropriate interpersonal style to reduce tension or conflict.					
37	While working on new ideas, I involve my students as well as others.					
38	I develop partnerships joining my area with the other ones to help achieve institutional goals.					
39	I consult my colleagues while preparing a new topic for teaching.					
40	I develop facilitative, influential interpersonal style to develop a team.					
41	I listen carefully and sensitively to stakeholders views/opinions.					

5) Research and Knowledge Transfer:

42	I identify new areas for learning.					
43	I apply new knowledge and skills to support the research process.					
44	I have quality of peer reviewed publications, keynote/ invited lectures.					
45	I organize and coordinate conferences/presentations/workshops/seminars. (strike out whichever is not applicable)					
46	I lead and manage research teams plus interdisciplinary research activities.					
47	I facilitate financial support to my college from research councils and other external bodies.					
48	I involve myself in knowledge/technology transfer with other institutions and private consultancy.					
49	I prepare research articles/ book chapters /books/ conference proceedings. (strike out whichever is not applicable)					
50	I have membership of professional body.					
51	I create link with professional societies/ trade/ academic bodies. (strike out whichever is not applicable)					
52	I have editorship or membership of editorial boards, journal refereeing.					

53	I write articles for non-academic media.					
54	I build up a base for internal and external contacts for self as well as college.					
55	I cultivate potential collaborations to maximise opportunities.					
56	I prepare 'live' networking strategy as an ambassador.					

6) Administrative, Technical and Professional Knowledge & Skills:

57	I formulate strategy, policy and planning.					
58	I attain a satisfactory level of administrative and technical knowledge.					
59	I lead and manage a group of staff within my authority.					
60	I interpret and manage a budget within budgeting guidelines.					
61	I manage my own time to accomplish task.					
62	I take global trends and feedbacks when planning for the future.					
63	I implement new innovative strategies and best practices across the college.					

7) Facilitating Changes:

64	I am considered as a role model for positive change by leading people.					
65	I plan, organize, facilitate and monitor changes within the college.					
66	I generate enthusiasm, commitment in members of the team for accepting changes and challenges.					
67	I ensure that individuals get the resources and support to facilitate changes.					

8) Creativity/Problem Solving :

68	I generate and promote new ideas.					
69	I challenge the status quo.					
70	I push the boundaries of my subject matter.					

71	I stay abreast of the latest academic and industry developments.					
72	I integrate the latest thinking with core principles of subject areas.					
73	I identify and define main problems/issues and suggest appropriate solutions.					
74	I choose the best tried and tested problem solving alternatives.					
75						

Thanks for your response